

THE SiC_p HYBRIDIZING EFFECTS ON THE PROPERTIES OF THE C/AL MMCS MANUFACTURED BY INFILTRATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the effects on the aluminum matrix composites by the SiC particles hybridized in the carbon fibers. It was demonstrated that these SiC particles could separate the clustered fibers which is beneficial to the vacuum pressure infiltration and to obtain a well fiber distribution. The improvement to the mechanical properties was determined and the microstructure was investigated to study the hybridizing effects on the infiltration and properties.

INTRODUCTION

Recent researches attach importance to the fiber reinforced metal matrix composites to achieve their superior properties and broad applications[1]. One technique for the production of such composites involves molten metal infiltration of fiber preform with the aid of external pressure[2], its attraction being a capability to produce net shaped, complex engineering components with high efficiency[3-7]. It is found that there have problems of bad wettability and chemical reaction occurring between reinforcement and matrix at the infiltration temperature. These problems hinder the improvement of the composites properties, make the infiltration difficult, and enhance the fabrication cost.

In the present paper, the method of fibers hybridized with SiC_p was applied to improve the compo-ability of high temperature reaction products. The carbon fibers were hybridized separately in three different SiC_p concentration solutions and one other fiber group was applied with fiber coating as well as hybridizing. The microstructure of the pure aluminum composites reinforced with above carbon fibers is studied using Scanning Electron Microscope(SEM) equipped with a energy spectrometer(EDAX). In parallel, mechanical properties of the composite are investigated using three-point bending tests and tensile tests. The relation between the properties and the microstructures is analyzed. It is demonstrated that the hybridizing SiC_p is effective on the improvement of the composites structures and properties.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composite materials studied were high purity aluminum A00(Al \geq 99.7%) reinforced with PAN-based carbon fibers. Nominal properties of the aluminum were: tensile strength 65MPa, tensile modulus 30GPa, failure strain 35%; Nominal properties of the PAN-II carbon fiber were: tensile strength 2000MPa, tensile modulus 250GPa, fiber diameter 6-8 μ m; another kind of carbon fiber was AS4C carbon fiber with the tensile strength of 2324 MPa. The hybridizing SiC particles were W05 SiC particles of the average diameter 2-5 μ m.

The fibers were disglued and then were dragged through hybridizing solutions which have different SiC particles contents. These solutions were kept agitating and ultrasonic vibrating. When the fibers were dragged through these solutions, they were relaxed by the ultrasonic cavitation effecting. So that the SiC particles can be hybridized into the fibers evenly. Fiber groups A, B and C stand for three different hybridizing concentration, Fiber group D was hybridized and simultaneously Sol-gel coated, Fiber group O was a sample group of untreated fibers for comparison purpose. The fiber treatment parameters were shown in the Table 1.

Table 1 Treating parameters for carbon fiber

Solution No.	Composition	SiC content (g/1000ml)	Taking up speed (cm/min)
O*	/	/	/
A	1000mlH ₂ O+5g[Na(PO ₃) ₆]	10	180
B	1000mlH ₂ O+5g[Na(PO ₃) ₆]	20	180
C	1000mlH ₂ O+5g[Na(PO ₃) ₆]	40	180
D**	polycarboliene+n-C ₆ H ₁₄	40	12

*: Group O, A, B, C fibers are PAN-II carbon fibers.

** : Group D fibers are AS4C fiber made in U. S. A, these fibers are SiC-coated as well as SiCp-hybridized, Its experiment results can be found elsewhere [8].

The preforms entwined with fibers were preheated and then infiltrated by liquid aluminum into solid composites. The infiltration procedure is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Temperature and pressure parameters used in infiltration process

The tensile specimens and bending specimens were carefully polished to reduce the influences of surface aspirates or tiny defects on the mechanical test.

Tensile tests were performed on Shimazu AG-10T testing machine at a crosshead speed of 0.3mm/min, gauge dimensions of the specimen is $2.5 \times 4 \times 40 \text{ mm}^3$. Three-point bending test were performed on the MTS-New810 testing instrument at a loaded deforming speed of 1 mm/min. Dimensions of the bending specimen is $2 \times 3.4 \times 30 \text{ mm}^3$.

Polished sections and fracture surfaces of composites were examined with a Philips SEM-515 microscope equipped with a PV-9900 EDAX spectrum. The fiber volume fraction was measured by using KONTRON Image Analyzer.

HYBRIDIZING FIBER AND COMPOSITE MICROSTRUCTURE

The fibers with hybridizing SiC particles are shown in Fig.2. The fibers treated in solution A were hybridized with a few SiC particles in a rather far distance between each other, see Fig.2(a). The fibers treated in solution B were adhered with a certain amount SiC particles with a middle distance, see Fig.2(b). The fibers treated in solution C were adhered with a large amount nodular SiC particles with a nearly scattered distribution. see Fig.2(c). By our experiment method, the amount of SiC particles in the solutions has a directly influence on the hybridizing that if the SiC particles amount in the solutions has a notable discrepancy, then the SiC particles hybridized in the fibers will has the similar discrepancy.

Fig.2 Surface morphology of carbon fiber hybridized with SiC particles in solution A(a), B(b) and C(c)

SEM-515 was used to observe the polished sections of composites. A transverse section of the composite, Fig.3, shows a uniform distribution of fibers in the bundle and no visible porosity at this magnification. Close fiber parking near the edge of the bundle is evidence of fibers being

forced together by the pressure of the liquid aluminum infiltration front. However, it is obvious that the close fiber parking in hybridized composite is not as serious as that of unhybridized one. Fig.4 were the photography of typical transverse section of the composite at a higher magnification. The fiber distribution in hybridized composites Fig.4(a) is fewer and evenly scattered than that of unhybridized composites, Fig.4(b).

Fig.3 Transverse section of infiltrated composite

Fig.4 Comparison of fiber distribution in hybridized composite(a) and unhybridized one(b)

Fig.5 Longitudinal section microstructure(a) and EDAX results(b) in material C

The evenly fiber distribution in Fig.4(a) was the consequence of the hybridizing SiC particles exiting between the fibers. In Fig.5, The particle indicated by an arrow in Fig.5(a) is a SiC particle widespread in the group C and D composites, which is analyzed by the EDAX as shown in Fig.5(b). The distance between two fibers hybridized with SiCp was 3-7 μ m, which is about half to one fiber diameter, and the dimension of the hybridizing SiC particles is 2-5 μ m, just a little than the fibers distance. We also find out in the polished section of unhybridized composite that the distance between fibers is very narrow comparing with 3 μ m. So the SiCp hybridizing is sufficient to separate fibers, hence to avoid fiber contacting and bundling and to obtain a more evenly fiber distribution with proper interspace.

The fiber volume fractions measured are listed in Table 2. The fiber volume in the composites decreased with increasing of the hybridizing SiCp amount. As discussed above, the decrease of fiber volume was also the diluting effect by SiCp hybridizing.

Table 2. Measured fiber volume fraction of C/Al composites

Sample area	O	A	B	C	D
Total transection	55.7	49.7	53.4	49.6	20
Fiber bundle	65	58	55	51	20

COMPOSITES PROPERTIES AND FRACTOGRAPHY

The tensile properties and bending properties of the C/Al MMCs are shown in Table 3. The ratio of the determined strength vs. ROM value increases because of the decrease of fiber volume in the hybridized composites. Both in tensile tests and bending tests, the ratios are rising as the hybridizing SiCp content increase as shown in Table 3. The value of average tensile strength/ROM of group C composite is 45% higher than that of group O composite. Furthermore from bending tests, such kind value calculated from group D composite is 252% as high as that from group O composite. These coincided with fracture feature of composites.

Table 3 Tensile and bending properties of the C/Al MMCs

Item	O	A	B	C	D
SiCp content, g/L	0	10	20	40	40
UTS, MPa	219.8	211.3	272.9	286.2	/
σ_B , MPa	312.4	405.1	/	540.2	355.2
V_f , %	5.7	49.7	53.4	49.6	20
ROM, MPa	1142.8	1026.7	1098.3	1024.8	516.8
UTS/ROM, %	19.23	20.56	24.85	27.93	/
σ_B /ROM, %	27.3	39.5	/	52.7	68.7

The composites interface under our manufacturing method is a strong-bonded interface which universally has a flat appearance with little fiber pullout, especially in regions where fibers were closely packed and poorly infiltrated. The second feature, presented in Fig.6(a), shows multiple fiber fracture with cracks propagating across fibers straightway when individual fibers are closely spaced. However, there are certain discrepancies on the fracture surface between composites with and without hybridizing, according to the fiber distribution and interface bonding. The fracture surface of group O composite, shown in Fig.6(a), is flat without any fiber

pullout or debonding, and the crack is cleaved through fibers. Such a fracture structure can only dissipate very limited fracture energy, resulting in the lowest mechanical properties. The hybridizing composites have better mechanical properties with appreciate changes on the fracture surface, as shown in Fig.6(b). The fibers generally have a certain degree debonding from the matrix as well as the crack propagation were hindered with a limited extent about several fibers distance. Further away from the fibers, however, plastic deformation of the matrix was evident. It is obviously that the properties in hybridized composites was enhanced due to much more fracture energy absorbed in the composite fracture procedure.

Fig.6 Fractography of C/Al MMCs
(a)unhybridized; (b)hybridized

HYBRIDIZING EFFECT ON THE PROPERTIES AND FRACTURE

The C/Al MMCs has the advantage of the strong bearing phase of high strength carbon fiber. To fully realized this, there are two demands. one is that the applied stress should be efficiently transferred from the matrix to the fibers by the internal shear stress[9], the other is that it acquires plastic fracture of fiber short pullout in the crack propagation[1].

In our experiments, the mechanical properties of the composite indicated that the potential of the material has by no means been realized, however, they were improved by the SiC particle hybridizing due to a mixture of influence factors. Firstly, the evenly scattered fiber distribution can avoid the failed stress transfer caused by the few or non matrix surrounding around the fibers. the reinforcing efficiency increased as the volume fraction of the fiber decreased[10]. Secondly, it may be consider that some reduction in the volume fraction of fiber used in making the composites might be beneficial in order to ensure that each fiber is entirely surrounded by aluminum. The stress concentration which builds up at the tip of a crack may then be absorbed in the relatively ductile matrix regions, reducing the likelihood of an entire fiber bundle fracturing.

By the meantime, the thicker reaction zones which activate crack propagation were separated by enlarged space between fibers due to hybridizing effects, as shown in Fig.7, which appreciates to the lagging of crack initiation and propagation, also beneficial to the enhancement of the composite properties. As had been indicated elsewhere[1][11], appropriate chemical reaction is optimum to the composite properties. Particularly, in Sol-gel coated composite group D, the reaction hindering layer of SiC coating is an additional effect appreciated to the high properties. Further TEM evaluation on the C/Al interface reaction is undergoing in Shanghai Jiao Tong University.

Fig.7 Schematic show of hybridizing effect on separating brittle reaction layer

CONCLUSION

The SiC particles evenly adhering on the carbon fibers can separate the clustered fibers finely even under applied pressure and make fibers surrounded with aluminum, resulting in a well fiber distribution, with different hybridized concentration in corresponding fiber volume fraction in the composites.

The tensile strength and bending strength are both gradually enhanced synchronously with the increased hybridizing concentration. Not only the matrix slip-ability in the more broad zone between fibers, but also the brittle reaction layers which were separated by the SiC particles can influence the crack nucleation and propagation, resulting in the improvement of the C/Al MMCs properties. The hindering layer against reaction by SiC coating in company with above two effects made the coated and hybridized composites obtain the optimum properties.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The present study is supported by China National Science Foundation under contract No 9590015-02

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